

In-service Simulation of Second Phase Particle Evolution in Zircalloys - preprint

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ABSTRACT

The size and distribution of the second phase particles (SPPs) in Zircaloy-2 and -4 are known to influence the corrosion performance of the alloys. Under irradiation, the structural and chemical properties of SPPs change, releasing solute to the surrounding matrix—a process that has been qualitatively correlated to reduced in-reactor corrosion resistance. Both alloys contain the $Zr(Fe,Cr)_2$ Laves phase, which is known to amorphize and dissolve, the rate of which has a positive dependence on neutron flux and fluence and is inversely proportional to temperature. In this study, the characterization of SPPs in quenched and annealed Zircaloy-4 has been carried out using advanced electron microscopy to generate a statistically reliable data set across a range of conditions. The data from this work was used to develop and calibrate a Kampmann-Wagner numerical (KWN) precipitation model. This model, scripted in MATLAB, predicts SPP evolution in Zircaloy-4 during quenching by considering concurrent SPP nucleation and growth in the grain interior and at grain boundaries, as well as subsequent annealing in the high-temperature α -Zr

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phase field. The KWN model has also been extended to incorporate an established SPP amorphization model and a novel irradiation-induced dissolution model to track chemical and structural changes during irradiation. The dissolution model balances ballistic dissolution with interface-controlled growth, accounting for variations in solute solubility and diffusion under irradiation, along with a heterogeneous solute distribution in the matrix. The predictions of this novel approach correctly capture the observed trends of dissolution as a function of flux and temperature, validated by new experimental data from neutron-irradiated Zircaloy-2 (32.4 displacements per atom at 320 °C). This work enhances our understanding of SPP behavior during processing and under irradiation while providing a predictive tool to evaluate in-reactor corrosion performance.

Keywords

Zircaloy, second phase particles (SPPs), irradiation, amorphization, dissolution, KWN model

Introduction

The corrosion resistance of Zircaloy-2 and -4, alloys that are commonly used as nuclear fuel cladding, is strongly influenced by the size and distribution of the second phase particles (SPPs).¹ Both alloys contain the $Zr(Fe,Cr)_2$ phase, which primarily exists as the C14 hexagonal Laves phase,² although the C15 cubic Laves phase has also been reported.³ The majority of studies in literature focus on this SPP as it is found in both alloys, although Zircaloy-2 also contains body-centered tetragonal $Zr_2(Fe,Ni)$.² While the thermomechanical processes associated with cladding fabrication have been optimized to achieve particle size distributions (PSDs) that enhance corrosion resistance, the SPPs undergo structural and chemical changes during irradiation, which

can negatively impact the in-reactor corrosion performance of the alloys.⁴ Therefore, a model capable of predicting the evolution of these SPPs through processing and during in-reactor operation is a powerful tool to aid end-of-life corrosion predictions.

There have been many attempts to model SPP evolution in Zircalloys, the most successful of which use the Kampmann-Wagner numerical (KWN) framework. The KWN model⁵ discretizes time into a large number of small timesteps and employs classical precipitation theory to track the full PSD, including metrics such as volume fraction, number density, and mean radius of the SPPs. Massih and Jernkvist⁶ initially attempted to simulate $Zr(Fe,Cr)_2$ evolution in Zircaloy-4 during thermomechanical processing by modeling the ternary system as a simpler pseudo-binary system, treating Fe and Cr together as a single solute phase. However, their approach did not use the KWN framework and steady-state nucleation conditions were assumed. Therefore, neither the instantaneous PSD nor the nucleation rate prior to achieving steady state were captured. Later, the same pseudo-binary approach was employed by Robson.⁷ Using the KWN framework, which was scripted in MATLAB, his model captured both thermal and irradiation effects, although quantitative validation was not performed.

Pressurized water reactors (PWRs) and boiling water reactors (BWRs) operate at intermediate temperatures of 270–330 °C; therefore, this temperature regime is the primary focus when modeling SPP amorphization under irradiation. The amorphization process of $Zr(Fe,Cr)_2$ under neutron irradiation was first described by Griffiths et al.⁸ and can be broadly categorized into three general regimes: at low temperatures (<80 °C), homogenous amorphization is observed with no change in SPP chemistry; at typical operating temperatures (270–330 °C), an amorphous rim with a reduced Fe concentration relative to the crystalline phase forms at the periphery of the SPP; and at high temperatures (>367 °C), amorphization is not observed. In the intermediate

regime, the growth rate of the amorphous rim increases with neutron flux and fluence but decreases at higher temperatures.

Several authors have attempted to model $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ amorphization,^{9–12} with the two most widely used models being those developed by Motta⁹ and Taylor.¹⁰ Motta and Lemaignan explain the amorphization process in terms of free energy; for amorphization to occur, the free energy change induced by irradiation must be greater than the free energy difference between the crystalline and amorphous phases. Their model assumes that the ballistic mixing of Fe across the SPP interface leads to a hypostoichiometric crystalline phase that is unstable with respect to the amorphous phase.

Two key improvements of the Taylor model over the Motta model are that it considers both flux and temperature effects, with the key difference in the mechanism being that Fe loss follows amorphization—the inverse of the Motta model. Neutron bombardment of the SPPs is assumed to cause homogeneous amorphization, with the amorphous fraction increasing with neutron flux and decreasing with temperature, as higher temperatures promote SPP recrystallization. At a constant flux and temperature, a steady-state amorphous fraction is obtained. Fe redistribution is critical in the Taylor model to stabilize the amorphous layer, under the assumption that the amorphous phase has an equilibrium Fe concentration (assumed to be 10 at.%). Therefore, there is a driving force for Fe to redistribute to the surrounding matrix, reducing the supersaturation of the amorphous phase. Once a critical amount of Fe is lost, the amorphous phase stabilizes and it is no longer thermodynamically favorable for it to recrystallize, leading to the formation of an amorphous rim. The amorphous zone growth rate is proportional to the rate of Fe transport through the amorphous layer, which is postulated to be driven by neutron flux because of the inverse relationship between temperature and amorphization.

While amorphization of the Zr(Fe,Cr)_2 phase under irradiation has been extensively discussed and modeled by several authors,^{9,10,13} experimental and modeling studies of SPP dissolution are lacking. Although data on dissolution is limited, some studies do report changes in precipitate diameter under irradiation, with the results summarized in figure FIGURE 1. Like amorphization, the dissolution rate increases with neutron flux and fluence, although the dependence on temperature is slightly more complex.

The temperature dependence of dissolution shows three distinct regimes: at low temperatures (≈ 80 °C), dissolution is inhibited, with limited solute redistribution thought to occur via ballistic mixing;⁸ in the mid-temperature range (260–340 °C), the dissolution rate peaks before decreasing towards the upper end of this regime;¹⁴ and at high temperatures (>340 °C), the dissolution rate approaches zero, with SPP growth reported in some cases.¹⁵ During dissolution of the amorphous phase, it has been reported that irregularities at the amorphous zone/matrix interface align with the basal plane, indicating a directional dissolution process.¹⁶ This dissolution process is thought to occur via a Zr self-interstitial atom (SIA) switch mechanism⁸ resulting from the enhanced diffusion of Zr SIAs along the basal plane relative to the c-axis.¹⁷ A comprehensive dissolution model that offers predictions comparable with empirical measurements is yet to be developed.

FIGURE 1: A summary of the literature data on $Zr(Fe,Cr)_2$ dissolution.^{14,15,18}

One of the most commonly applied irradiation-induced precipitate dissolution models is the Nelson-Hudson-Mazey (NHM)¹⁹ model, which proposes that precipitate dissolution under irradiation is primarily driven by the recoil of atoms to the matrix caused by collision cascades. This is balanced by the growth of precipitates through thermally-activated diffusion. Overall, a process of inverse coarsening is predicted, with the precipitates eventually converging to an equilibrium size.

To the present authors' knowledge, only one attempt has been made to model the dissolution behavior of Zircaloys. However, this previous study acknowledged that further experimental analysis, along with a deeper fundamental understanding of solute evolution in zirconium during irradiation—particularly diffusion and solubility—is required to quantitatively validate the model. Robson²⁰ proposed that an increase in matrix solute solubility leads to the destabilization of the SPPs. He suggested that the observed decrease in dissolution rates at higher temperatures is caused by a reduction of the irradiation-enhanced solute solubility, which approaches equilibrium levels at an empirically determined maximum temperature. Although an

exact physical mechanism for this process was not provided, it was assumed that, at elevated temperatures, increased thermal annealing of defects, such as vacancies and dislocation loops, reduces the effective solubility.

In this study, we present a KWN model capable of tracking $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ SPP evolution in Zircalloys during thermomechanical processing and in-reactor operation. The model incorporates mechanisms for SPP nucleation and growth during β -quenching and captures the effects of neutron irradiation, i.e., SPP amorphization and dissolution. Through calibration and comparison with experimental data, the model provides semi-quantitative predictions and valuable insights into the mechanisms driving SPP evolution both with and without irradiation, supporting estimations of corrosion performance throughout the lifetime of Zircaloy clad materials under reactor conditions.

Materials and Methods

SAMPLE PREPARATION AND IRRADIATION CONDITIONS

Recrystallized annealed Zircaloy-4 sheet with a composition of $\text{Zr-0.99Sn-0.32Fe-0.19Cr-0.004Ni}$ (at.%) was used for quenching and annealing studies. Samples were heated above the β -transus ($1050\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), held for 30 min in an Ar atmosphere, and quenched in air (AQ), oil (OQ), and water (WQ) before some of the samples were subsequently annealed at $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a preheated furnace under an Ar atmosphere for 2 and 4 h, designated as AQ2, AQ4, OQ2, OQ4, WQ2, and WQ4.

Recrystallized annealed Zircaloy-2 sheet with a composition of $\text{Zr-1.03Sn-0.28Fe-0.17Cr-0.11Ni}$ (at.%) was irradiated in the BOR-60 test reactor at $320 \pm 10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under an approximate average neutron flux of $6 \times 10^{14}\text{ n cm}^{-2}\text{ s}^{-1}$. The final fluence was $1.62 \times 10^{22}\text{ n cm}^{-2}$, which corresponds to 32.4 displacements per atom (dpa).²¹

Full details on sample preparation for scanning electron microscopy with secondary

electrons (SEM-SE), backscattered electrons (SEM-BSE), and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) can be found elsewhere.²²

ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

Details on SEM-SE, SEM-BSE, and STEM imaging conditions are available elsewhere.²² Semi-quantitative STEM-EDX analysis utilized the Cliff-Lorimer approach, following the same methodology described by Harte et al.^{23,24}

Particle size analysis was carried out using ImageJ,²⁵ with the equivalent diameter of the SPPs calculated using their area. The interaction depth of BSEs was estimated to be 25 nm using the CASINO Monte Carlo software,²⁶ while electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) was used to determine the thickness of selected STEM samples.²³ A summary of the imaging procedures, along with the stereological equations used to determine SPP number density and volume fraction for each of the techniques are given elsewhere.²²

THE MODEL

KWN Precipitation Model

The basis of the KWN model has been extensively described in other studies.^{7,27} The present work builds on an existing model⁷ and extends its capability to simulate quenching and annealing in Zircaloy-4. Generally, in precipitation models, the first consideration is nucleation from a supersaturated solid solution. However, STEM-EDX observations indicated that the distribution of solute throughout the microstructure was not homogenous in the as-quenched samples. The formation of an inhomogeneous solute distribution is attributed to solute segregation during quenching. A previous approach²² modeled this using the Scheil equation.²⁸ However, as the Scheil model is strictly only valid for solidification, a simplified and more computationally efficient approach is utilized here. An empirical relationship, based on the relative volume fraction of SPPs

located at the grain boundary (GB) and within the grain interior (GI), was used to determine the concentration of solute for each region as a function of quench rate (QR). The fraction of solute at the grain boundary, f_{gb} , is given by equation (1), with the remainder assigned to the GI.

$$f_{gb} = 0.95 \exp(-0.0002QR) \quad (1)$$

The system can be viewed as two distinct mechanisms, with nucleation and growth mechanisms occurring in the GI and at the GB, as outlined in the following sections. Assuming the β -Zr to α -Zr transformation occurs faster than nucleation, the onset of nucleation for both GI and GB SPPs is determined using a relationship derived from Massih,²⁹ i.e., at the end of the phase transformation. The diffusion of solute across the grain and between the GB and GI was found have negligible effects on the model outputs.

Nucleation and Growth in the Grain Interior

The nucleation rate in the GI was determined according to classical precipitation theory (equation 1 in²⁷). However, Stowell's approach,³⁰ which equated the number of homogenous nucleation sites to the total number of solute atoms per unit volume, led to overpredictions of the nucleation rate compared with experimental data. This discrepancy indicated that SPPs nucleate on heterogeneous sites where the energy barrier to nucleation is reduced. STEM observations corroborated this hypothesis,²² with SPPs found on or near dislocations, suggesting that quench-induced dislocations serve as primary nucleation sites. A relationship was used to convert dislocation density to nucleation site density,³¹ which was then utilized with previously reported dislocation density measurements³² of an as-quenched Zr-Cr-Fe alloy, producing an effective nucleation site density in the GI as a function of QR .²²

Nucleation on dislocations reduces the associated strain energy, which reduces the critical radius, r^* , and the energy barrier to nucleation, ΔG^* .²⁷ To account for this, it is common practice

to pragmatically fit the interfacial energy within the model, thereby accounting for this reduced energy barrier to nucleation. A value of 0.18 J m^{-2} was found to produce a good fit to the most extreme experimental conditions, i.e., WQ and AQ.

Subsequent growth and coarsening of SPPs in the KWN model is typically captured through a mean-field approximation that assumes diffusion-controlled growth and considers capillarity effects through the Gibb-Thomson equation (equations 11 and 12 in²⁷). However, like grain boundaries, dislocations act as solute diffusion pathways, leading to enhanced growth. Their growth was captured through an existing dislocation-controlled growth model given by Ardell.³³ The constants and variables are described in detail elsewhere²² with one minor change to the area of dislocation in contact with the SPP, $q \text{ (m}^2\text{)}$, now being equal to $q = 4\pi r r_{\text{dis}}$, where r is the radius of the SPP (m).

Solute pipe diffusion via dislocations is known to be enhanced relative to bulk diffusion,³⁴ with the activation energy thought to be similar to GB diffusion.³⁵ With no better data currently available, solute diffusion through dislocations is taken to be the same as GBs (see Table 1).

Nucleation and growth at grain boundaries

GBs also reduce the associated strain energy with nucleation, although they are more efficient nucleation sites than dislocations. The interfacial energy was fitted in the same manner as above, with a value of 0.15 J m^{-2} providing a reasonable fit to the data. The GB nucleation site density, $N_{\text{gb}}^{\text{het}}$, is given in Table 1. If it is assumed that the supply of solute from the matrix is slow compared to the redistribution of solute via the GB, solute diffusion fields can overlap on the GB, leading to localized coarsening between these SPPs.³⁶ Ardell³³ provides a radial growth law for such SPPs, with a full analysis of the equations, variables, and constants provided in a previous study.²²

Annealing

Annealing from a recrystallized condition is assumed to be controlled by a universal SPP growth mechanism (equations 11 and 12 in²⁷), with solute diffusion through the bulk being the rate-limiting step. Given that Cr diffusion through the matrix is several orders of magnitude slower than Fe, SPP growth is limited by Cr. Notably, Cr exhibits diffusional anisotropy, diffusing more rapidly along the c-axis direction relative to the basal plane.³⁷ This anisotropy introduces variability into the model and is therefore used to set confidence limits. The interfacial energy was calibrated using the model, with a value of 0.2 J m^{-2} producing the best fit to experimental data, representing a slight reduction from values used in previous studies.^{6,7}

The evolution of an as-quenched microstructure to a recrystallized one is more complex. During this process, the system tends to minimize stored energy through the annihilation of dislocations and a reduction of grain boundary area via grain growth. Therefore, as a simplification, the KWN model assumes a transition to a bulk-diffusion-controlled growth mechanism during post-quench annealing. As demonstrated in the following section, this approach effectively captures SPP evolution, as the majority of SPPs are thought to grow through this mechanism, although it is acknowledged that some remain at GBs.

TABLE 1: Parameter values used in the KWN model to simulate SPP evolution during quenching and annealing		
Parameter	Value	Source
Effective particle composition, C_p (at. frac)	0.66	Versaci and Ipohorski ³⁸
Effective solubility limit, C_e^a (at. frac)	$\exp\left(\frac{-5400}{T} - 3.3\right)$	Various ³⁹⁻⁴³
Molar volume, V_m ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	9×10^{-6}	Gros and Wadier ⁴⁴
Effective diffusivity in the matrix, D_m ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$9.47 \times 10^{-6} \exp\left(\frac{-1.61}{k_b T}\right)$ to $2.35 \times 10^{-6} \exp\left(\frac{-1.39}{k_b T}\right)$	Hood and Schultz ³⁷
Effective diffusivity on grain boundaries, D_{gb} ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$727 \exp\left(\frac{-138,000}{RT}\right)$	Corvalán Moya et al. ⁴⁵
Effective diffusivity through dislocations, D_{dis} ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$727 \exp\left(\frac{-138,000}{RT}\right)$	Corvalán Moya et al. ⁴⁵
Interfacial energy of matrix SPPs, λ_m (J m^{-2})	0.2	Calibrated
Interfacial energy of GB SPPs, λ_{gb} (J m^{-2})	0.15 ± 0.02	Calibrated
Interfacial energy of dislocation SPPs, λ_{dis} (J m^{-2})	0.18 ± 0.02	Calibrated
Dislocation nucleation site density, N_{dis}^{het} (m^{-3})	$9.2 \times 10^{19} QR^{1.27}$	Sun and Northwood ³²
Grain boundary nucleation site density, N_{gb}^{het} (m^{-3})	$d_{gb} n^{Zr} S_v$	This work
Grain boundary area per unit volume, S_v ($\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-3}$)	$3 \times 10^4 QR^{0.7}$	This work
Grain boundary energy, σ_{gb} (J m^{-2})	0.3–0.9	Plowman and Race ⁴⁶
Grain boundary width, d_{gb} (nm)	0.5–1.3	Plowman and Race ⁴⁶

Atomic number density of Zr, n^{Zr} (m^{-3})	4.3×10^{28}	Arblaster ⁴⁷
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Irradiation Models

Amorphization

The amorphous zone thickness, δ (nm), is determined using the Taylor model.¹⁰ The release of Fe to the matrix during amorphization is tracked using the Fe concentration profile and volume fraction of each SPP size class. The Fe concentration is taken as 20 at.% at the crystalline/amorphous interface¹² and 44 at.% in the crystalline phase.^{38,39} This latter value is different for Zircaloy-2 (33 at.%)³⁸ and can be changed within the KWN model. Based on a recent APT study⁴⁸ and this work (as discussed later), the equilibrium Fe concentration in the amorphous phase and at the amorphous/matrix interface is assumed to be 3 at.%. Once an SPP becomes fully amorphous, the Fe concentration decreases at a rate governed by the neutron-flux-assisted diffusion coefficient, D_a^{Fe} ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), defined as:⁴

$$D_a^{\text{Fe}} = k_1^{\text{D}} \phi - k_2^{\text{D}} \quad (2)$$

where k_1^{D} and k_2^{D} are empirically fitted constants determined by Robson as $3.48 \times 10^{-41} \text{ m}^4 \text{ n}^{-1}$ and $2.61 \times 10^{-24} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively.¹²

While the Taylor model provides good predictions of the amorphous zone thickness, neither it nor the Motta model account for a dose-to-amorphization, despite evidence of this in the literature.^{8,14,49} The dose-to-amorphization is critical to capture solute evolution during the early stages of irradiation and has been accounted for using an adapted form¹⁴ of a rate theory model for electron-induced amorphization of intermetallic compounds given by Motta and Olander:⁵⁰

$$D^{\text{am}} = D_0^{\text{am}} + \frac{A}{n\sqrt{\phi}} \exp\left(\frac{-Q}{2k_b T}\right) \quad (3)$$

where D^{am} is the dose-to-amorphization ($\text{n cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and D_0^{am} represents the athermal dose-to-amorphization at low temperatures when annealing effects are minimal, assumed to be 0 dpa under neutron irradiation based on current evidence.⁵¹ The activation energy, Q , which represents the dominating annealing defect, was determined to be 1.38 eV. The flux dependency is controlled by n , with a value of 8 producing a good fit to the available data, indicating a relatively weak dependence on neutron flux. k_b and T have their usual meanings, while A is treated as a normalizing constant ($4.33 \times 10^{32} \text{ n}^{1/8} \text{ cm}^{-1/4} \text{ s}^{-1/4}$).

As the original form of the Taylor model does not include a dose-to-amorphization, an enhancement factor is included to increase the rate at which amorphization progresses once the critical dose is exceeded, matching the predicted δ . In addition, irradiation-induced dissolution decreases the total SPP diameter, meaning the reported amorphization widths, which the Taylor model is calibrated to, represent the observed amorphization width rather than the true amorphization width. An additional enhancement factor is incorporated to account for this.

Dissolution

There are several different approaches that can be used to model the dissolution of SPPs under irradiation. The simplest approach is an empirical fit, the details of which can be found elsewhere.²² However, in an attempt to develop more meaningful models and enhance our mechanistic understanding of the process, the present study focuses on two approaches: i) the NHM model in its original form¹⁹ and ii) a modified cellular NHM (MNC) model that considers additional factors, overcoming the shortcomings of the original NHM model. Both models are calibrated using the data from Bajaj et al.¹⁴ Given the added complexity at very high temperatures, these models focus on dissolution under conditions relevant to PWRs and BWRs, spanning an approximate temperature range of 260–340 °C. In this range, amorphization will occur, thus dissolution is only

considered for the amorphous phase. At higher temperatures (above 340 °C), Zr(Fe,Cr)₂ SPPs likely remain crystalline. In such cases, the balance between SPP dissolution and growth is expected to follow a different mechanism.

As Cr is a slower diffuser relative to Fe,³⁷ it is assumed to be rate controlling in the dissolution process. Consequently, this section focuses on Cr rather than the effective Fe and Cr solute used earlier.

NHM Model

The original NHM framework considers the ballistic sputtering of atoms from the SPP to the matrix as the sole driving force for dissolution, counteracted by SPP growth. As the KWN model explicitly tracks the solute concentration in the matrix, a simplified version of the NHM model is given as:

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = -\zeta K \frac{1}{N} + \frac{3D_{\text{irr}}C_i}{4\pi r C_p} \quad (4)$$

The first term on the right-hand side (RHS) of the equation represents the reduction in SPP radius caused by the ballistic sputtering of atoms, where ζ describes the flux of atoms sputtered across the interface, K is the damage rate, and N is the atomic density. The second term on the RHS of the equation takes the irradiation-altered diffusivity, D_{irr} , instantaneous solute concentration in the matrix, C_i , concentration of solute in the SPP, C_p , and SPP radius, r (m), to determine SPP growth. Notably, this term is flawed as it does not account for solute solubility. Therefore, in the absence of irradiation, the model predicts that SPPs will grow indefinitely. Previous studies have addressed this issue by introducing capillarity effects;⁵² however, irradiation likely alters the delicate interfacial compositions that develop under equilibrium conditions.

The NHM model makes two critical assumptions: 1) ballistically sputtered atoms are instantaneously relocated in the matrix to infinite distances, and 2) recoil events do not transport

solute atoms back to the SPP.⁵³ A recent heavy ion irradiation experiment has shown that at doses of 24 dpa, no observable change in SPP morphology is seen, although there is some atomic mixing of Cr across the SPP/matrix interface.⁵⁴ This suggests that ballistic mixing alone cannot account for the dissolution of these SPPs. Aside from differences induced by the type of irradiation, e.g., cascade size, the major difference between heavy ion and neutron irradiation is the timescale, with the former typically achieving equivalent doses in hours compared with years. Therefore, the subsequent diffusion distance of ballistically ejected solute atoms to the far-field matrix will be significantly reduced, indicating that solute diffusion away from the SPP is a critical factor. This is also corroborated by observations made after low-temperature neutron irradiation experiments.⁸

Attempts were made to calibrate the NHM model using the data of Bajaj et al.¹⁴ by varying ζ and D_{irr} ; however, it was not possible to replicate the trends of $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ dissolution, i.e., limited dissolution at both high temperatures (≈ 330 °C) and very low temperatures (≈ 100 °C). The growth term in the NHM model is a function of SPP size, leading to an overall prediction of inverse coarsening. As temperature increases, D_{irr} increases accordingly, which shifts the predicted equilibrium size—the diameter at which the smallest SPPs will grow to and the largest ones shrink to—to higher values. It does not, however, appreciably reduce the dissolution rate of the dissolving SPPs. Therefore, modifications to this model are required to successfully replicate the dissolution trends of $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ SPPs.

MNC Model

The current diffusion-controlled growth mechanism in the NHM model assumes solute homogeneity in the matrix (mean-field approximation); however, STEM-EDX analyses of neutron-irradiated $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ SPPs in Zircaloy-2 show a high Cr concentration adjacent to dissolving SPPs, decreasing further into the matrix (indicated by ref.²⁴ and data presented later in

this work). These findings suggest that Cr diffusion in the matrix is limited, leading to a heterogeneous distribution and invalidating the mean-field approximation. To address this, an interface-controlled growth mechanism, combined with ballistic sputtering, is suggested to control the dissolution behavior of the $Zr(Fe,Cr)_2$ amorphous phase under irradiation. This mechanism follows Christian's^{31,55} model for interface-controlled growth:

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = M\Delta G_g \quad (5)$$

where M is the mobility of the interface ($m\ s^{-1}\ mol\ J^{-1}$) and ΔG_g ($J\ mol^{-1}$) is the driving force for growth, which are given as:

$$\Delta G_g = RT \ln \left(\frac{C_{if}}{C_{eq}^{Cr}} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$M = \frac{bv_j}{RT} \exp \left(\frac{Q_i}{RT} \right) \quad (7)$$

Here, b is the jump distance (m), which is taken as the lattice spacing in the basal plane;¹⁶ v_j is the jump frequency (s^{-1}), approximated as $k_b T/h$, where h is Planck's constant (J s); Q_i is the activation energy for atomic transfer across the interface ($J\ mol^{-1}$); C_{eq}^{Cr} is the equilibrium solubility of Cr, which is thought to change under irradiation, leading to an irradiation-enhanced solubility (C_{irr}^{Cr}); and C_{if} is the concentration of Cr at the interface. C_{if} is tracked by solving Fick's second law using an explicit finite difference method.⁵⁶ This approach models Cr released from dissolving SPPs and its diffusion through the matrix, controlled by D_{irr} and assuming a consistent concentration profile for every SPP. The overall growth rate is given by equation (8), with four critical parameters to be determined: ζ , Q_i , C_{irr}^{Cr} , and D_{irr} .

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = -\zeta K \frac{1}{N} + M\Delta G_g \quad (8)$$

The vacancy concentration under irradiation is thought to play a crucial role in both $C_{\text{irr}}^{\text{Cr}57}$ and D_{irr} .⁵⁸ Computational studies^{59,60} show that the vacancy concentration in Zr significantly increases under irradiation, from $2 \times 10^{-7}\%$ at 10^{-8} dpa up to 0.02% at 1 dpa⁵⁹ or 3% at 4 dpa.⁶⁰ Assuming the value at 10^{-8} dpa is close to the vacancy concentration in the absence of irradiation, these studies provide a broad range of vacancy supersaturation levels of 10^5 – 10^7 . Jain et al.⁵⁸ reported that the fast interstitial diffusers in α -Zr exhibit positive drag ratios, meaning that vacancies bind to these solutes and diffuse as vacancy-solute pairs. As vacancies diffuse slower, the overall diffusivity is reduced as the vacancy concentration increases. The range of mentioned diffusivities was investigated and compared with experimental data obtained from STEM-EDX analysis in the present work. A higher vacancy supersaturation of 10^7 was found to be reasonable, although a further reduction of the solute diffusivity by an order of magnitude was required to reproduce experimental observations.

From a thermodynamic perspective, for an SPP to destabilize under irradiation, there must be an increase in the effective solute solubility in the matrix, i.e., $C_{\text{irr}}^{\text{Cr}}$. Although no mechanistic model currently predicts this increase precisely, computational studies have demonstrated that vacancies can accommodate up to 3–4 Fe or Cr atoms,⁵⁷ while atom probe tomography (APT) characterization has shown evidence of an increased Cr concentration in the matrix after irradiation.⁴⁸ It may be possible to determine an increase in solubility as a function of fluence, flux, and temperature; however, given the complexity involved with this calculation, $C_{\text{irr}}^{\text{Cr}}$ is empirically set at 0.03 ± 0.02 at.%. This range is based on data extracted from an APT study.⁴⁸

Robson²⁰ suggested that the enhancement in solute solubility under irradiation decreases

at higher temperatures, eventually falling to equilibrium levels, explaining the reduced dissolution rates at higher temperatures. In the present approach, the balance between ζ and Q_i introduces a dynamic transition temperature between SPP dissolution and growth. This temperature evolves as solute is ballistically sputtered from the SPP and subsequently diffuses away from the interface, causing variations in solute supersaturation at the interface.

A thorough investigation of Q_i is possible via density functional theory, although this is beyond the scope of the present work. Here, Q_i is calibrated against experimental data. Similarly, the ballistic sputtering parameter, ζ , has not been explicitly studied in Zr alloys. The original NHM model suggested a value of 10^{18} atoms m^{-2} dpa^{-1} . However, recent studies on precipitates in Fe-Cr alloys provide higher ranges of 1.4×10^{20} – 1.2×10^{21} (irradiation with heavy ions)⁶¹ and 7×10^{19} – 4.5×10^{20} atoms m^{-2} dpa^{-1} (irradiation with protons and heavy ions).⁶² Although Fe-Cr alloys differ from the system under investigation, these results provide a reasonable starting range for model calibration. The dissolution model achieves a good fit to the experimental data of Bajaj et al.¹⁴ using $Q_i = 211$ kJ mol^{-1} and $\zeta = 3.5 \times 10^{20}$ atoms m^{-2} dpa^{-1} .

The model accounts for the back-sputtering of solute atoms from the matrix to the SPP by comparing the concentration of Cr in the matrix adjacent to the SPP with the concentration of Cr within the SPP, overcoming limitation (2) of the NHM model described above. The effective growth rate caused by ballistic mixing is determined as the positive form of the first term on the RHS of equation (4). Through this method, the ballistic dissolution term cancels out once the Cr concentration in the matrix adjacent to the SPP equals that of the SPP. This adjustment is particularly crucial at high dose rates or low temperatures.

TABLE 2: MNC model parameters and a summary of the key assumptions and simplifications used

Parameter	Value	Source
Irradiation-altered solubility, $C_{\text{irr}}^{\text{Cr}}$ (at.%)	0.03 ± 0.02	Eriksson et al. ⁴⁸
Irradiation-altered diffusion, D_{irr} ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$\begin{cases} 1.42 \times 10^{-19} \exp\left(\frac{-0.46}{k_b T}\right), & \text{if } T < 548 \text{ K} \\ 5.76 \times 10^{-7} \exp\left(\frac{-1.83}{k_b T}\right), & \text{if } T \geq 548 \text{ K} \end{cases}$	Calibrated using the present work and Jain et al. ⁵⁸
Ballistic sputtering parameter, ζ ($\text{atoms m}^{-2} \text{dpa}^{-1}$)	3.5×10^{20}	Calibrated, Zhao et al., ⁶¹ and Thomas and Was ⁶²
Activation energy of Cr transfer across interface, Q_i (kJ mol^{-1})	211	Calibrated
Amorphous SPP atomic density at the interface, N (atoms m^{-3})	Zircaloy-4 = 3.85×10^{28} ; Zircaloy-2 = 4.62×10^{28}	Versaci and Ipohorski ³⁸
Atomic fraction of Cr at amorphous/matrix interface	Zircaloy-4 = 0.39; Zircaloy-2 = 0.485	Versaci and Ipohorski ³⁸ and this work
Assumption/simplification	Justification	
The model only considers dissolution of the amorphous zone. If no amorphous rim forms, dissolution is not modeled.	This model is only applicable to temperatures ranges where the formation of an amorphous rim is expected in $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ SPPs. Moreover, at low irradiation doses, an incubation period to dissolution is expected, like amorphization. At higher temperatures, the SPPs are crystalline and a different dissolution (or growth) mechanism is assumed.	
SPP coarsening is not accounted for, meaning SPPs cannot grow beyond their initial size.	SPP growth has only been reported at temperatures exceeding the valid temperature range for this model.	
Irradiation-altered solubility and diffusion are assumed to be constant.	While these parameters likely evolve gradually over the course of irradiation, the model assumes that once the dose-to-amorphization threshold is exceeded, steady-state conditions are reached.	
A total simulation cell size of $5 \mu\text{m}$ is used to model Cr diffusion in the matrix, with individual segment widths of 1 nm.	This combination of parameters is a balance between speed and accuracy, with this bin width proving suitable for the range of conditions tested here. Given the limited diffusion distance of Cr, a $5 \mu\text{m}$ cell width is sufficient.	
Neutron flux is converted to a damage rate assuming 1 dpa is equivalent to $5 \times 10^{20} \text{ n cm}^{-2}$.	This conversion has been suggested in the literature. ⁶³	

Results and Discussion

SPP EVOLUTION DURING QUENCHING AND ANNEALING

Experimental Characterization

The microstructures of the as-quenched Zircaloy-4 samples are displayed in figure FIGURE 2. Initial observations indicated that the OQ sample exhibited two distinct microstructures, likely caused by a delay in part of the sample entering the oil after removal from the furnace, herein referred to as slow oil-quenched (SOQ) and fast oil-quenched (FOQ). The cooling rates for AQ, SOQ, FOQ, and WQ were calculated to be 6–20, 60–590, 309–817, and 1000–3000 K s⁻¹, respectively. These estimates were determined by measuring the widths of the α -Zr lathes and using equation 2.1 from Massih et al.,⁶⁴ along with experimental data for very fast quench rates.⁶⁵ Each of the four samples exhibited a Widmanstätten basketweave structure, a result of the random precipitation of α -Zr grains because of the low impurity content in the alloy (e.g., C and Si).⁶⁶ Faster cooling rates resulted in an increased undercooling from β -Zr to α -Zr, leading to a higher nucleation rate of α -lathes and decreased lath widths. It was also observed that the SPPs, which appear black against a gray matrix during SEM-BSE imaging, were more concentrated at grain boundaries (GBs) relative to the grain interior (GI) in AQ and SOQ.

FIGURE 2: SEM-BSE micrographs of (A) AQ, (B) FOQ, (C) SOQ, and (D) WQ.

A typical $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ SPP found in AQ was indexed as the C14 hexagonal Laves phase, consistent with previous investigations of this alloy.⁶⁷ A summary of the statistical SPP data obtained via electron microscopy is given in Table 3.

TABLE 3: A summary of SPP data for the quenched and annealed Zircaloy-4 samples

	Mean (nm)				Mode (nm)				Number density (μm^{-3})				Volume fraction			
	SEM- SE	SEM- BSE	STEM-EDX		SEM- SE	SEM- BSE	STEM-EDX		SEM- SE	SEM- BSE	STEM-EDX		SEM- SE	SEM- BSE	STEM-EDX	
			GB	GI			GB	GI			GB	GI			GB	GI
AQ	144 ± 3.1	80 ± 1.1	137 ± 5.0	102 ± 16.2	95 ± 5	45 ± 5	90 ± 5	40 ± 5	0.30	12.7–14.6	4.4–5.8	0.4–0.6	0.0057	0.0087– 0.0118	0.0087– 0.0120	0.0004– 0.0006
AQ2	158 ± 2.7	90 ± 5	0.34	0.0078
AQ4	171 ± 3.4	100 ± 5	0.32	0.0086
SOQ	...	50 ± 0.4	35 ± 5	14.7–33.2	0.0031– 0.0077
FOQ	13 ± 0.6	7 ± 0.9	7 ± 1	3 ± 1	588–906	166–260	0.0086	...	0.0011– 0.0018	0.0002– 0.0003
OQ2	139 ± 3.2	95 ± 5	0.50	0.0078
OQ4	171 ± 3.6	175 ± 5	0.30
WQ	9 ± 0.4	6 ± 0.2	9 ± 1	6 ± 1	3160– 6620	6630– 13900	0.0014– 0.0030	0.0008– 0.0017
WQ2	90 ± 2.1	75 ± 5	0.90	0.0063
WQ4	112 ± 3.3	100 ± 5	0.60	0.0071

As the resolution limit of SEM analysis is on the order of a few tens of nm, STEM-EDX was the only technique capable of detecting SPPs in each of the as-quenched samples. For this analysis, it was determined that the oil-quenched sample was FOQ rather than SOQ. As expected, slower quench rates resulted in an increased mean and modal SPP diameter with a reduced number density.

The ratio of GB to GI SPPs decreased as the quenching rate increased, whilst across every sample, the mean and modal diameter of the GB SPPs was greater than the GI SPPs. The volume fraction and number density of GI SPPs were reduced relative to the GB SPPs in AQ and FOQ, whereas WQ exhibited the opposite trend. These results confirm a quench-rate-dependent partitioning effect of solute during quenching as β -Zr transforms to α -Zr, along with separate precipitation mechanisms for the GB and GI SPPs.

As evidenced by the SEM-SE data, post-quench annealing led to an increase in both the mean and modal diameter, while the number density generally decreased.

Simulating SPP evolution

Figure FIGURE 3 presents a comparison between the model predictions and experimental data from Gros and Wadier.⁴⁴ At lower temperatures and shorter annealing times, an average diffusivity between the c-axis and a-axis directions produces the best agreement with experimental measurements. However, at higher temperatures and longer annealing times, the model indicates that Cr diffusion parallel to the a-axis direction becomes rate controlling. This transition occurs as the system progresses further into the coarsening regime, increasing the interparticle spacing and the diffusion distance of Cr released from dissolving SPPs. Consequently, diffusion in the a-axis direction begins to control the rate of SPP growth.

FIGURE 3: Predictions of the KWN model compared with data from Gros and Wadier for a range of annealing temperatures.⁴⁴

Figures 4a and 4b compare the as-quenched outputs of the model with the experimental data reported Table TABLE 3. This data shows the combined information from GB and GI precipitates.

The model predicts SPP number density well (fig. 4a), particularly at the fastest quench rates. The biggest discrepancies between the model and experiment are SEM-BSE analysis of SOQ ($60\text{--}590\text{ K s}^{-1}$) and SEM-SE analysis of AQ ($6\text{--}20\text{ K s}^{-1}$). In SEM-BSE, these differences are primarily due to the resolution limits of the microscope, along with a minimum detection limit of 30 nm. In SEM-SE, smaller SPPs may be lost during mechanical grinding and polishing, along with the possible dissolution of smaller SPPs during etching.⁴⁴

Similarly, the model's predictions of mean SPP diameter (fig. 4b) generally agree with experimental observations, except for the AQ sample measured by SEM-SE and STEM. In SEM-

SE analysis, the loss of smaller SPPs and microscope resolution limits skew the mean diameter toward a larger value. This latter point also applies to the SEM-BSE measurements of SOQ. For STEM measurements of AQ, the foil thickness was determined using EELS, which limited sampling to specific regions. In this case, a single grain. Therefore, the data is unlikely to be comprehensively representative, indicating that SEM-BSE is the most useful technique for this sample. Unlike the faster-quenched samples, SEM-BSE analysis is not limited for this sample as the minimum SPP size detected in AQ was greater than the minimum detection limit (30 nm).

The model predictions for post-quench annealing at 700 °C are shown in figures 4c–4e, providing insight into the influence of thermomechanical processing. The model predicts the evolution of the modal diameter well, with one notable discrepancy being OQ4, which is likely related to sampling errors (11 SPPs were 175 ± 5 nm, while 9 were 125 ± 5 nm), particularly when compared with AQ4.

Although the quenching conditions have a very strong influence on the initial modal diameter, this effect diminishes with further annealing at 700 °C because of the rapid growth of small SPPs relative to larger ones. For similar annealing times at lower temperatures, e.g., during a stress-relief anneal rather than a recrystallization anneal, the initial quenching conditions have a more pronounced impact on the final PSD.

FIGURE 4: Total (A) number density and (B) mean radius measured experimentally and predicted by the KWN model across a range of quench rates, and (C), (D), and (E) evolution of modal diameter during post-quench annealing at 700 °C.

SPP EVOLUTION UNDER IRRADIATION

Experimental characterization

Figure 5 shows STEM-EDX images of $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ SPPs in Zircaloy-2 before and after neutron irradiation to $16.2 \times 10^{21} \text{ n cm}^{-2}$ (32.4 dpa). In the unirradiated sample, the Fe/Cr ratio was 0.98 ± 0.07 . As expected, the Fe and Cr concentration in the matrix were below EDX detection limits. The mean SPP diameter was determined to be $49 \pm 26 \text{ nm}$, based on 1007 measurements. The number density and volume fraction were estimated to be within $54\text{--}92 \text{ SPPs } \mu\text{m}^{-3}$ and $0.0042\text{--}0.0072$, respectively.

After irradiation to 32.4 dpa, noticeable changes in SPP morphology were observed. The

SPP/matrix interface became irregular, with the Fe/Cr ratio map emphasizing these irregularities, potentially indicating preferential dissolution in the basal plane direction. In addition, there was segregation of solute in the matrix in bands parallel to the basal plane. The Fe/Cr ratio in these bands is lowest closest to the SPP and increases with distance from the SPP/matrix interface. This is a consequence of a higher Cr concentration closer to the SPP, whilst Fe is relatively homogeneously dispersed throughout the matrix. A convergent beam electron diffraction pattern taken from the center of one SPP confirmed that the phase was amorphous.

Adjacent to a Cr-rich amorphous shell, remnants of a partially dissolved $Zr_2(Fe,Ni)$ SPP were seen in figure 5c. Fe remained slightly enriched in both types of SPP relative to the matrix, but the Fe/Cr ratio has decreased to approximately 0.1 in both $Zr(Fe,Cr)_2$ SPPs (figs. 5b and 5c). Assuming the Cr concentration remained the same in the amorphous phase, this indicates that the Fe concentration within this phase is approximately 3 at.%, in agreement with a previous APT study.⁴⁸ The line profile shows that the Cr concentration was highest in the amorphous zone (0–25 nm), remained elevated in the matrix close to the SPP/matrix interface (25–50 nm), and dropped significantly but remained above baseline levels at intermediate distances (50–150 nm). Beyond 150 nm, the Cr concentration approached the EDX detection limit.

FIGURE 5: Evolution of SPPs in Zircaloy-2 irradiated in the BOR-60 reactor. EDX maps show net counts individually scaled for each map, while the Fe/Cr ratio map and line scan of Cr concentration show at.%. Regions in the Fe/Cr maps of 0 indicate that one or both solute elements was below the noise threshold limit of 1 at.%.

MNC model predictions

The evolution of the average dissolution rate predicted by the MNC model as a function of temperature and neutron flux/dose rate is shown in figure 6. The model successfully captures the three distinct regimes of dissolution observed experimentally under neutron irradiation (fig. 6a). At low temperatures (≈ 80 °C), the dissolution rate is limited because solute diffusion away from the interface is inhibited. This leads to solute accumulation at the interface, where back-sputtering of atoms from ballistic collisions counteracts dissolution caused by collisions with the SPP. This also explains the behavior seen during short irradiations with a high damage rate, such as heavy ion irradiations.

As temperature rises, diffusivity increases, facilitating Cr migration away from the interface. This reduces both back-sputtering and solute supersaturation at the interface, decreasing

the driving force for growth and steadily increasing the dissolution rate.

In the mid-temperature range (260–340 °C), the dissolution rate reaches its peak. This peak is the result of an optimal balance between solute diffusion away from the interface and interface mobility (M). At this peak temperature, thermal diffusion of solute to the far-field matrix reduces supersaturation at the interface, decreasing back-sputtering and the thermodynamic driving force (ΔG_g) for growth, while M remains sufficiently low to limit interface-controlled growth. The precise temperature of this peak shifts with neutron flux. Beyond the peak temperature, the dissolution rate decreases sharply as M becomes dominant. Approaching 330 °C, ballistically sputtered atoms are rapidly reincorporated into the SPP, leading to negligible dissolution rates.

This analysis also provides insights into the relationship between flux and temperature. The temperature of peak dissolution increases with flux because the optimal balance of solute diffusion to the far-field matrix and M occurs at higher temperatures for higher fluxes. At low temperatures, the effects of neutron flux diminish and the dissolution rates converge. In this regime, diffusion of solute away from the interface is negligible and it quickly supersaturates the region near the SPP. As the solute concentration in the matrix adjacent to the SPP rapidly equals that of the SPP, ballistic sputtering effects cancel out, leading to similar average dissolution rates across all flux levels.

The error bars in this plot were generated using the range of $C_{\text{irr}}^{\text{Cr}}$ values from Table 2. At low temperatures, changes in solubility have negligible effects. The primary factor limiting the dissolution rate at these low temperatures is the back-sputtering of atoms, which is not affected by $C_{\text{irr}}^{\text{Cr}}$. In the mid-temperature region, variations in $C_{\text{irr}}^{\text{Cr}}$ have a more pronounced impact on the dissolution rate. At these temperatures, interface-controlled growth, i.e. $\Delta G_g M$, becomes comparable to the ballistic dissolution rate. As a result, changes in $C_{\text{irr}}^{\text{Cr}}$ and the subsequent effect on ΔG_g have a more pronounced influence on the overall dissolution rate.

Across all flux levels, a notable step-change in dissolution rate occurs at approximately 298 °C, deviating from the general trend. This is thought to be a modelling artefact resulting from uncertainty in some of the input parameters.

Having established the general trends of the MNC model, it is useful to compare its predictions with experimental results. Garzarolli et al.¹⁵ reported an average initial SPP diameter of 340 nm in Zircaloy-4 that reduced to 240 nm after irradiation to 1.1×10^{22} n cm⁻² at an average flux of 0.92×10^{14} n cm⁻² s⁻¹ and a temperature of 290 °C. From a similar starting mean size of 346 nm, the MNC model predicts a final mean diameter of 240 nm with lower and upper bounds of 235 and 252 nm, respectively, closely matching experimental observations. This agreement demonstrates the model's ability to predict Zr(Fe,Cr)₂ dissolution under typical reactor conditions.

Further validation comes from data obtained from the high-flux BOR-60 test reactor (fig. 5). Although a full post-irradiation statistical analysis is not yet available, after 32.4 dpa, amorphous shells remain in the matrix. Starting from the mean SPP diameter of 49 nm, an earlier empirical model²² predicts complete SPP dissolution, while the original NHM model (lacking solute distribution considerations) predicts rapid and complete dissolution of the SPPs. Contrastingly, the MNC model predicts a reduction in mean SPP diameter to 13 nm with bounds of 12–16 nm, aligning with the experimental observations that amorphous shells remain.

The discrepancy between both the empirical and NHM models compared with the MNC model arise because the flux is increased by an order of magnitude relative to typical operating conditions, leading to a corresponding increase in the ballistic dissolution rate. For a given fluence, shorter irradiation times under high-flux conditions limit solute diffusion in the matrix, causing solute accumulation at the SPP/matrix interface. This results in solute supersaturation, promoting interface-controlled SPP growth and reducing the dissolution rate. Neither of the former models

consider this aspect.

The robustness of the model is further illustrated by simulating extreme conditions that extend beyond the calibrated range. Figure 6b shows the dissolution rate at three different dose rates, representing neutron, proton, and heavy ion irradiations, each simulating a total dose of 10 dpa. It is important to note that calibration of the MNC model has been performed using a limited set of neutron irradiation data,¹⁴ whereas a comprehensive validation of these predictions requires thorough post-irradiation SPP characterization across the range of dose rates. Nevertheless, a notable comparison can be made with a heavy ion irradiation (Kr^{17+}) at 400 °C with a dose rate of $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dpa s}^{-1}$ to a maximum dose of 20 dpa at the Bragg peak, approximately averaged out throughout the irradiated region as $3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dpa s}^{-1}$ and 13 dpa.⁶⁸ The mean size of the $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ SPPs was reported to reduce from 92 to 56 nm. Under these conditions, the MNC model predicts an average dr/dpa of $-1.55 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m dpa}^{-1}$, close to the reported dr/dpa of $-1.4 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m dpa}^{-1}$, demonstrating the predictive accuracy of the model under extreme conditions.

The MNC model effectively predicts the dissolution of $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ SPPs across varied conditions, indicating that the mechanism of dissolution has been successfully captured. Its ability to replicated trends under extreme conditions highlights its potential to serve as a tool to simulate in-reactor operation and guide future irradiation experiments, from which it can be further calibrated and verified.

FIGURE 6: The average dissolution rate predicted by the MNC model for (A) varying neutron fluxes for an irradiation time of one year and (B) for three different dose rates to a total dose of 10 dpa.

The MNC model has been used interchangeably across Zircaloy-2 and Zircaloy-4 as it considers the variation in Cr concentration between the typical SPPs found in the two alloys (see Table 2). As a brief comparison, a similar simulation was carried out with the input parameters of a typical $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe},\text{Cr})_2$ SPP found in Zircaloy-4 (lower Cr concentration), using the same conditions as the BOR-60 results presented in figure 5. The predicted final mean diameter of the Zircaloy-4

SPPs was 8 nm, indicating that the lower concentration of Cr leads to an increased dissolution rate. This is expected as less Cr is released to the matrix for a given change in SPP diameter; therefore, the solute supersaturation at the interface and driving force for growth is reduced. Moreover, assuming ζ is constant, the reduced N of the SPPs in Zircaloy-4 leads to an increased rate of ballistic dissolution.

It is important to note that the MNC model parameters given in Table 2 are unlikely to be finalized. Ongoing work aims to further validate the model and refine these parameters using $\text{Zr}(\text{Fe,Cr})_2$ dissolution data across both Zircaloy-2 and -4, while also extending the model's temperature range. In addition, investigations are underway to expand the KWN model to include $\text{Zr}_2(\text{Fe,Ni})$, enabling predictions of both SPP phases in Zircaloy-2 during irradiation.

Conclusions

The characterization of SPPs in Zircaloy-4 was conducted using a range of techniques, each with benefits and drawbacks depending on sample preparation and the SPP size distribution. STEM proved effective at imaging the smallest SPPs, while SEM, particularly using BSEs, offered improved statistical accuracy when imaging larger SPPs. These data were used to develop a KWN model capable of tracking SPP evolution during quenching and annealing of Zircaloy-4, accounting for two distinct mechanisms of SPP nucleation and growth, as well as solute segregation during quenching. SPP nucleation in the grain interior is closely related to the dislocation density, with subsequent growth controlled by solute diffusion through these dislocations. At grain boundaries, enhanced nucleation and growth are also predicted.

SPP amorphization was simulated using an established sub-model that considers a balance between the formation of homogenous amorphous zones, driven by neutron flux, and thermal annealing, driving recrystallization. Concurrent SPP dissolution was modeled using a novel

approach combining aspects from existing models. The ballistic sputtering of atoms, driving dissolution, was combined with an interface-controlled growth mechanism that considers irradiation-induced changes to solute solubility and diffusivity, while also accounting for a heterogeneous solute distribution in the matrix. The model correctly predicts the experimentally observed trends, effectively capturing the effects of neutron flux, fluence, and temperature on SPP behavior and overcoming some key limitations from earlier approaches. A notable application includes the ability to estimate SPP evolution under ion irradiation, aiding future experimental design. Moreover, it is anticipated that this modelling methodology can be applied to other SPP systems containing a slow-diffusing solute element that controls dissolution.

The sub-models used to predict SPP evolution under irradiation were incorporated within the KWN framework, creating a MATLAB-based unified model capable of predicting SPP evolution from thermomechanical processing through to in-reactor operation.

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